

THE 2019 INDUSTRY FORUM

PROCEEDINGS DOCUMENT

NAVIGATING DEVELOPMENT OF U.S. OFFSHORE WIND

Sustainability and Co-Existence through Science

Co-convended by:

College of Earth, Ocean,
& Environment

SPECIAL INITIATIVE ON OFFSHORE WIND

Sponsors

The Industry Forum has benefited from the generous sponsorship gifts of several of COL's member institutions, federal agencies with responsibilities in this area, industry partners, and other nongovernmental organizations. All involved see the collective benefit of bringing together diverse stakeholders to discuss the future of development of U.S. offshore wind and of working together to advance the science that guides decision making in all sectors. Please join us in thanking them for their generous support, which has allowed us to bring this group together.

OCEAN SUSTAINER

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CONTRIBUTING PARTNERS

Dear Participants,

Thank you, again, to everyone who participated in the 2019 Industry Forum – ***Navigating Development of U.S. Offshore Wind: Sustainability and Co-Existence through Science*** – convened by the Consortium for Ocean Leadership (COL) in collaboration with the Special Initiative on Offshore Wind. The Forum was well-attended and included stakeholders and experts representing multiple sectors engaging around the benefits and challenges of developing an equitable offshore wind energy industry in the United States. We took great care in listening to and working with you to accurately capture the range of views and outcomes of discussion, which are laid out in this proceedings document (without attribution).

Due to the complexity of developing offshore wind energy in the United States, science and technology must serve as the foundation for the path forward. From a science-based understanding, decisionmakers in all sectors will be equipped with the best available information to make wise decisions that ensure our ocean remains healthy and productive for all. This is the goal of our work, and we at COL look forward to working with you as our partner stakeholders on next steps.

We are grateful for the collaboration with the Special Initiative on Offshore Wind in convening the Industry Forum. The event has also benefited from the generous sponsorship (and time) of several of our member institutions, federal agencies with responsibilities in this area, industry partners, and other nongovernmental organizations that see the collective benefit of bringing together diverse stakeholders to discuss how we can work together to advance a science-based, sustainable, economically viable offshore wind energy industry. Thanks to their support, we were able to bring this group together to address this important topic.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, reading "Jonathan W. White". The signature is fluid and cursive, with a long, sweeping underline that extends to the left.

RADM Jonathan W. White, USN (ret.)
President and CEO
Consortium for Ocean Leadership

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- 8:00 a.m. Continental Breakfast
- 8:30 a.m. Welcome
 Nancy Sopko, Special Initiative on Offshore Wind
 Jonathan White, Consortium for Ocean Leadership
- 8:45 a.m. Opening Keynote Remarks
 Walter Cruickshank, Bureau of Ocean Energy Management
 Jon Hare, NOAA Northeast Fisheries Science Center
- 9:15 a.m. Reducing Impacts to Protected Species in Balance with Offshore Wind Needs and Constraints
This panel focused on the principle impact-producing factors and the means to reduce those impacts. It also considered the impact of mitigation measures on project viability, as well as what further work is needed in the areas of science, policy, regulation, regional planning, among others.
Moderator: Brian Hooker, Bureau of Ocean Energy Management
 Catherine Bowes, National Wildlife Federation Northeast Regional Center
 Vicki Cornish, Marine Mammal Commission
 Sophie Hartfield Lewis, Ørsted North America
 Sean Hayes, NOAA Northeast Fisheries Science Center
 Scott Kraus, New England Aquarium
- 10:30 a.m. Coffee Break
- 10:45 a.m. Achieving Effective Co-Existence of Fishing Activities and Offshore Wind
This panel considered the views of fishing stakeholder communities, current efforts to mitigate presumed harmful impacts, and possible action, policy, or management needs.
Moderator: Annie Hawkins, Responsible Offshore Development Alliance
 Beth Casoni, Massachusetts Lobstermen's Association
 Peter Hughes, Atlantic Capes Fisheries, Inc.
 Andrew Lipsky, NOAA Northeast Fisheries Science Center
 Noah Oppenheim, Institute for Fisheries Resources
 Ruth Perry, Shell Exploration and Production Company
 David Rudders, Virginia Institute of Marine Science
- 12:15 p.m. Lunch and Sponsor Showcase Preview
- 1:00 p.m. Exploring the Scientific and Economic Opportunity Space of Offshore Wind
This panel explored what opportunities offshore wind will create for advancing science and technology in the marine realm, as well as the economic developments that might spin-off from offshore wind and its associated infrastructure.
Moderator: Steve Lohrenz, University of Massachusetts Dartmouth
 Jocelyn Brown-Saracino, DOE Wind Energy Technologies Office
 Robert Griffin, University of Massachusetts Dartmouth
 Anthony Kirincich, WHOI Wind Energy Technology Program
 Rachel Pachter, Vineyard Wind
- 2:30 p.m. Coffee Break
- 3:00 p.m. Spotlight on Recommendations and Actions
 Jon Hare, NOAA Northeast Fisheries Science Center
 Annie Hawkins, Responsible Offshore Development Alliance
 Brian Hooker, Bureau of Ocean Energy Management
 Steve Lohrenz, University of Massachusetts Dartmouth
 Ruth Perry, Shell Exploration and Production Company
- 3:45 p.m. Summary and Closing Remarks
 Nancy Sopko, Special Initiative on Offshore Wind
 Jonathan White, Consortium for Ocean Leadership
- 4:15 p.m. Sponsor Showcase and Networking
- 5:30 p.m. Adjourn

Executive Summary

On October 25, 2019, the Consortium for Ocean Leadership, in partnership with the Special Initiative on Offshore Wind, hosted its fifth annual Industry Forum in Washington, D.C., entitled ***Navigating Development of U.S. Offshore Wind: Sustainability & Co-Existence through Science.***

Offshore wind is a new and rapidly growing segment of the U.S. energy sector, currently off states along the East Coast of the United States, with future development projected off California, Oregon, the Hawaiian Islands, and Great Lakes coasts. Investments over the last half-decade are estimated to be in the hundreds of millions of dollars, and more recently, in the sale of over \$400 million in new federal lease areas by the Department of the Interior in 2018 with additional anticipated lease auctions to continue in 2020. These investments, coupled with increased demand in state procurements for renewable energy and evolving state and federal policies, will add approximately 26,000 MW of additional renewable offshore wind power to the Northeast and Mid-Atlantic energy markets by 2030. Recent analysis has further suggested that building and installing the requisite infrastructure will generate U.S. supply chain, infrastructure, and manufacturing demands in the billions of dollars.

The objectives of the forum were to:

- Determine the current status of U.S. offshore wind development, including impacts, available science, and current federal regulatory frameworks.
- Identify offshore wind opportunities for the U.S. Blue Economy, particularly in the advancement and growth of ocean science and technological innovation.
- Develop recommendations for investment priorities for science and technology, management strategies, and policies to ensure the sustainable development of offshore wind energy.

While current and future investments in offshore wind development will contribute to renewable energy and related segments of the Blue Economy, there are many unanswered questions regarding the potential impacts to marine life, biological and physical ocean processes, and fishing communities. The forum sought to delve into these questions with the help of subject matter experts in their respective fields. The forum identified key issues to bring to policy makers' attention, with participants generating action items to be undertaken by the offshore wind industry and sectors impacted by offshore wind development. These priorities and outcomes fell within a handful of overarching themes:

- The need for collaboration across the various sectors and constituencies;
- Establishment of a scientific funding mechanism;
- Adaptive pathways that enable the collection of scientific data as part of offshore wind development;
- Open and honest communication that includes engagement amongst key affected interests;
- A regional approach that supports and enhances our existing scientific enterprise;
- Innovation to provide real-time, sustained ocean monitoring and observations; and
- Opportunities for workforce development for offshore wind projects, the supply chain pipeline, and ancillary areas.

The concluding panel, "Spotlight on Recommendations and Actions," delved into these themes, identifying specific needs that emerged from previous panels as critical starting points for industry and government focus.

Forum Overview

The Industry Forum is an annual meeting designed to bring together academia, industry, nonprofits, and the government to explore pressing issues of mutual concern that involve ocean industries. The 2019 Forum was convened on October 25 to focus on the sustainable development of U.S. offshore wind energy. It was designed to consider many aspects of the U.S. offshore wind industry, including the reduction of impacts to protected species, achieving effective coexistence between the fishing and offshore wind industries, and exploring the scientific and economic opportunities that exist in U.S. offshore wind development. The Forum was not designed to generate precise and actionable consensus agreements but rather to encourage the exchange of information and perspectives to generate insights and momentum for addressing key challenges and opportunities for advancing the development of U.S. offshore wind energy.

Offshore wind is a new and rapidly growing segment of the U.S. energy sector, currently off states along the East Coast of the United States, with future development projected off California, Oregon, the Hawai'ian Islands, and Great Lakes coasts. Investments over the last half-decade are estimated to be in the hundreds of millions of dollars, and more recently, in the sale of over \$400 million in new federal lease areas by the Department of the Interior in 2019 with additional anticipated lease auctions to continue in 2020. These investments, coupled with increased demand in state procurements for renewable energy and evolving state and federal policies, will add approximately 26,000 MW of additional renewable offshore wind power to the Northeast and Mid-Atlantic energy markets by 2030. Recent analysis has further suggested that building and installing the requisite infrastructure will generate U.S. supply chain, infrastructure, and manufacturing demands in the billions of dollars.

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- Identify offshore wind opportunities for the U.S. Blue Economy, particularly in the advancement and growth of ocean science and technological innovation.
- Develop recommendations for investment priorities for science and technology, management strategies, and policies to ensure the sustainable development of offshore wind energy.

The Forum consisted of keynote presentations and panel discussions designed to encourage robust dialogue and exchange on science and technology needs, environmental and regulatory issues, finance and investment, and public perception. During the concluding panel, recommended actions were identified based on discussion during previous panels.

Opening Keynote Remarks

The Forum opened with selected speakers from the federal government who gave brief remarks to set the stage for the day's discussion.

Remarks by Dr. Walter Cruickshank, Acting Director, Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (BOEM)

The Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (BOEM) relies on robust environmental studies and assessments for science-based decisions about offshore wind energy regulation and development. There are currently 15 active offshore wind energy leases in the Atlantic, totaling about 1.7 million acres, with an increased number of plans from those leaseholders to expand to bid on additional leases. BOEM is planning to hold additional lease sales off the coasts of New York, North Carolina, Oregon, and the Gulf of Maine in the years to come. While this progress is positive, a concerted effort is needed to reduce potential conflicts with other ocean users, mitigate the impacts of development, and ensure a reliable domestic supply chain for these activities. BOEM recognizes the need to identify best practices for project design in order to establish a strong foundation for all projects going forward. BOEM is therefore taking a long-term view of offshore wind development by conducting a cumulative impacts analysis of projects in the pipeline. This means that any leasing of areas on the Outer Continental Shelf must consider how development activities will impact other ocean users and the environment. Additionally, BOEM is committed to a robust permitting process that evaluates environmental impacts, as well as the impacts to other ocean users, to determine how these impacts can be mitigated. This evaluation must include broad stakeholder and public engagement. Dr. Cruickshank reiterated BOEM's commitment to forging new partnerships to engage local and regional fishing interests throughout the offshore wind permitting process, with the goal of bringing their expertise into the discussion and ensuring that the best science and practices come into management processes. BOEM is heavily involved in scientific research; the goal is to learn more and consider the local and regional concerns of fishing communities in the development of offshore wind energy. Dr. Cruickshank ended his remarks by expressing the need to strike a balance between protecting sustainability and productivity and allowing the U.S. to continue domestic energy development in the hopes of one day achieving domestic energy independence.

Remarks by Dr. Jon Hare, Director, Science and Research, NOAA Northeast Fisheries Science Center

There has been a wave of challenges and opportunities in the country's pursuit of offshore wind development and the goal must be co-existence of renewable energy development with sustainable fisheries, wildlife protections, and our ocean ecosystems. The only way to reach all three elements of this goal is through collaboration, requiring a regional approach to ecosystem-based decision-making and planning, as well as innovative approaches. Dr. Hare highlighted the work of the Responsible Offshore Science Alliance (ROSA), a broad membership-based coalition of fishing industry associations and fishing companies, offshore wind developers, and state and federal government agencies with an interest in improving the compatibility of new offshore development with commercial fishing businesses. The group is promoting and building a regional science framework with the three-fold goal of renewable energy development, sustainable fisheries, and wildlife protections. Their work could serve as a model to other regions and should be replicated. Efforts to address the regional scientific needs for effective management and conservation of wildlife and ocean ecosystems are also being advanced by similar models. Dr. Hare closed his remarks with a renewed call for collaboration and to implement innovative approaches to resolve conflicts and achieve our goals.

Panel Summaries

The majority of the forum was structured into a series of four panels in which diverse panelists reflected on the status of the U.S. offshore wind industry and the potential impacts development could have on fisheries, protected species, and other marine life, and discussed possible solutions to those challenges. Panels were organized as discussions, encouraging engagement with participants in question-and-answer sessions to identify challenges and opportunities. Perspectives from panelists and participants are summarized below.

Reducing Impacts to Protected Species in Balance with Offshore Wind Needs and Constraints

Brian Hooker *Bureau of Ocean Energy Management, Moderator*

Catherine Bowes, *National Wildlife Federation*

Vicki Cornish, *Marine Mammal Commission*

Sophie Hartfield Lewis, *Ørsted North America*

Sean Hayes, *NOAA Northeast Fisheries Science Center*

Scott Kraus, *New England Aquarium*

This panel focused on the principle impact-producing factors of offshore wind development and the means to reduce those impacts on protected species. The panel also considered the impact of mitigation measures on project viability, as well as what further work is needed in the areas of science, policy, regulation, and regional planning, among others. As the moderator, Brian Hooker opened by asking the panel for their views of the single biggest environmental stressor from offshore wind project construction or operation and what solutions provide the most hope. The consensus from the panelists was that underwater noise associated with offshore wind development could have significant environmental impacts, most notably from construction-related activities, and the possible displacement of marine life because of noise. However, the panelists raised concerns about other threats including the impacts of turbine structure and energy absorption and disruption to local ecosystems. Panelists found encouragement in a number of approaches, including real-time monitoring, collaboration on data collection, moving construction work to a time when marine mammals are not in the area, and the approach from state governments to build protections for marine life into their decision-making process.

Several technologies were identified that can help mitigate offshore wind farm construction sound. These include bubble curtains, sleeves, and shells, all of which can be implemented to dampen the noise associated with pile-driving activities. There is also an emerging technology called “blue piling,” which uses a large column of water to drive a pile into the seabed. This new technology has the potential to significantly reduce offshore wind farm construction noise to an even greater degree. Furthermore, there were other new platform technologies discussed that could eliminate or reduce the need for pile driving, such as gravity-based foundations and floating structure technology.

The discussion then focused on data collection, collaborative research, and regional science efforts. The panelists expressed the strong need for a regional view because many of the species that require protection are highly migratory. There was agreement that one offshore wind energy developer cannot be expected to cover an entire region. Regional planning is also a hot topic as it pertains to the North Atlantic right whale. Massachusetts is doing good work in setting baseline science standards going forward, with funding for that effort coming from state and federal agencies and offshore wind developers. It is critical that many entities contribute to funding research projects so that the integrity of the data can be maintained. Offshore wind developers are also constantly collecting data, so there needs to be a concerted effort to use that data and to ensure that it can be accessed by relevant stakeholders.

As noted, concerns were expressed over the North Atlantic right whale and how offshore wind development could impact that endangered species. The North Atlantic right whale has been in a state of decline since around 2010 and there are currently only about 400 left. Both survival rates and reproduction rates have declined to dangerously low levels. Scientists often do not know where or when the whales are in a certain area. Acoustic

data shows that they go everywhere at all times, but we are now seeing a major shift in North Atlantic right whale over-wintering habitat which now coincides with the Southern New England Wind Energy areas, making it difficult to limit mitigation measures to seasonal restrictions.

There is concern among the fishing community that offshore wind development is going to change the ecosystem characteristics in ways that are not yet fully understood due to changes in the local and regional oceanographic hydrodynamics and the resulting changes to habitat, plankton communities and larval transport. The offshore wind industry looks closely at hydrodynamics, which are also factored into BOEM studies.

It was also noted that NOAA Fisheries is developing large ecosystem-linking models that can be scaled. The challenge is linking small-scale turbines into larger-scale ecosystems. A national and regional focus, therefore, is best because focusing on the impact of an individual project will make it very difficult to determine whether the impact came from the individual project or climate change at that limited view.

The panel concluded with the panelists agreeing that climate change is the challenge of our generation, so it is in everyone's best interest to figure out a path forward on offshore wind development.

Achieving Effective Coexistence of Fishing Activities and Offshore Wind

Annie Hawkins, *Responsible Offshore Development Alliance, Moderator*

Beth Casoni, *Massachusetts Lobstermen's Association*

Peter Hughes, *Atlantic Capes Fisheries, Inc.*

Andrew Lipsky, *NOAA Northeast Fisheries Science Center*

Noah Oppenheim, *Institute for Fisheries Resources*

Ruth Perry, *Shell Exploration and Production Company*

David Rudders, *Virginia Institute of Marine Science*

This panel addressed the views of fishing communities, current efforts to mitigate presumed harmful impacts, and possible action, policy, or management needs. Moderator Annie Hawkins opened by stating that science is going to be the solution to co-existence between the offshore wind and commercial fishing industries.

The panel discussion first set the stage of how offshore wind development could potentially change the marine physical and biological environment. While panelists posed several questions, there was agreement that exactly how offshore wind development will change the marine environment remains unknown. This uncertainty can be addressed by adapting our scientific enterprise and ensuring regional collaborative science is initiated at the appropriate scales.

The ability to fish among fixed structures, like offshore wind turbines, depends on such factors as the space between the fixed structures, their orientation, and how much scour exists around the base of the structures. Interestingly, the commercial fishing community has not defined the exact spacing required for fishing in and around wind turbines for particular fish species and catch mechanisms. Additional navigational concerns such as line of site and radar interference when fishing near wind turbines also require further scientific inquiry and investment.

The commercial fishing representatives on the panel and invited audience also made the strong point that commercial fishing is a culture and livelihood for those that practice it. As such, this should be considered when engaging these communities and discussing the planning and implementation of offshore wind structures or any other use of the ocean that directly impacts them.

There was a general call for multi-year baseline studies to be done so that changes in the environment can be documented, studied, and monitored over time. Because the marine environment is dynamic, it is possible that a new ocean user, like the offshore wind industry, would change those dynamics. There was general agreement that coexistence between the fishing and offshore wind industries is vital. Engagement with the fishing industry must occur early and often, and such engagement would benefit from a formal mechanism to inform fishermen collectively.

A question was posed from the audience about the potential impacts of offshore wind development to National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) surveys. Offshore wind development is both a challenge to continuing science surveys and an opportunity because there are so many possible solutions to these challenges from the science and technology arena. We need sustainable energy and sustainable fisheries and to protect marine habitats and endangered species. NOAA's current protected species and fisheries surveys represent some of the most comprehensive data on marine ecosystems in the world. They support fisheries assessments and management actions, protected species assessments and management actions, ecosystem-based fisheries management, and regional and national climate assessments, as well as a number of regional, national, and international science activities. Much of this data is also relied upon by developers and BOEM in planning offshore wind projects. However, if we do not begin investing in adapting these surveys so they are compatible with wind energy development we risk our ability to effectively manage fish stocks and manage protected species such as North Atlantic right whales. There was a call for more enhanced models, partnerships, and cross-sector collaboration, as well as investments in solutions from the science and technology world, such as new survey protocols and detection systems, calibration of time series, and other forms of data collection.

In the Gulf of Mexico, oil and gas development has achieved full engagement with the fishing industry. There are now recreational fishermen in the Gulf who call the oil and gas companies to tell them about the concerns they have about taking the structures out of the ocean floor. In the Atlantic, the offshore wind development is just getting underway, presenting a real opportunity to build strong relationships at this early stage. Solutions can be found if the right people are engaged early and often, as demonstrated by with the formation of the Responsible Offshore Science Alliance (ROSA). Impacts do not always have to be negative; they can be positive and mutually beneficial, too, especially if stakeholders work together on solutions.

A critical topic of discussion was the potential for further collaboration between the offshore wind industry, the fishing industry, environmental nonprofits, and research institutions. Panelists agreed that a collaborative, science-driven approach has been most effective when incorporated into adaptive regulatory models and processes. Managers and regulators at all levels should engage with all interested parties, and all interested parties need to come to the table focused on finding solutions. For example, researchers at the University of Massachusetts Dartmouth are engaging fishermen as the platform to gather data, which further connects them to that data and science. This approach will also help build trust across sectors, which is currently still a challenge. Importantly, this is not a data-deficient landscape, but rather, an information-deficient landscape, which requires synthesis to understand what the data is saying through a participatory process.

The panel acknowledged that as offshore wind projects move through construction and into operations, current data gaps will need to be filled through ongoing monitoring and observations, allowing for scientific analysis of environmental impacts. Such efforts could also lead to the development of science and technology solutions, as well as best management practices for Atlantic operations. Development is not done in a vacuum, and today's hypotheses could be real-world tested so that the three-pronged goal of advancing development, environmental sustainability, and protection of ocean-dependent communities can be achieved.

Exploring the Scientific and Economic Opportunity Space of Offshore Wind Development

Steve Lohrenz, *University of Massachusetts Dartmouth, Moderator*

Jocelyn Brown-Saracino, *DOE Wind Energy Technologies Office*

Robert Griffin, *University of Massachusetts Dartmouth*

Anthony Kirincich, *WHOI Wind Energy Technology Program*

Rachel Pachter, *Vineyard Wind*

This panel explored the opportunities offshore wind development will create for advancing ocean science and technology in the marine realm, as well as the economic opportunities that could spin off from offshore wind development and its associated infrastructure. While there will be ancillary and indirect economic and scientific benefits, the projected direct economic benefits are also impressive, and there is much to be learned from the European experience about cost reduction and understanding the costs and benefits of offshore wind

development in the Atlantic. Indeed, there is enormous opportunity to leverage offshore wind and its infrastructure to increase our knowledge of what is happening in the ocean. Offshore wind farms could be designed to also function as experimental test beds where scientific questions and operational challenges can be investigated. However, the science and technology priorities must be selective and have broad support in order to investigate and answer the most relevant and critical scientific questions. There are many examples of how offshore wind infrastructure and operational methods can be leveraged to advance ocean science and technology.

- Floating LIDAR buoys are currently used by offshore wind developers, such as Ørsted, for data collection and validation of turbine placement plans. There is interest in also equipping them to collect other environmental measurements. Co-funding opportunities are available to support implementation of some of these ancillary augmentations, but there needs to be cross-sector support for using these tools in this dual manner and agreement on the specific data they collect at what standard.
- Offshore wind structures could be used to establish a large acoustic monitoring platform that could serve science, conservation, fishermen, developers, and other stakeholder communities. A regular maintenance schedule could monitor such issues as pile driving sound and ship engine noise, and this data does not have to be proprietary.
- Development and use of autonomous applications are exploding in many sectors and offshore wind could offer an environment in which these tools are advanced in unique ways. Particularly, services such as operations, communication, battery life and recharging can be developed into a supporting network for open water applications.

At the same time, there was agreement that the priority should be on getting the first tranche of offshore wind projects through the permitting and development process in a streamlined way before looking at ancillary use projects and the permitting they will entail. However, once the first generation of offshore wind projects are in place, focus can turn to development of ancillary uses, and how to incorporate design plans for future-use projects in the siting and development phase for subsequent projects.

There was some discussion about bringing the U.S. Integrated Ocean Observing System (IOOS) into the fold. The IOOS has data repositories and aggregators and is building a knowledge network to support data-driven decisions by such groups as local fishermen. There is currently a movement underway to implement an IOOS-like arrangement for offshore wind-specific interests and data, and the IOOS experience could inform best practices for acquiring, archiving, and sharing data.

In summary, there is now an incredible opportunity space not previously available associated with development of offshore wind energy for the investigation of critical geoscience questions.

Spotlight on Recommendations and Actions

Jonathan White, *Consortium for Ocean Leadership, Moderator*

Jon Hare, *NOAA Northeast Fisheries Science Center*

Annie Hawkins, *Responsible Offshore Development Alliance*

Brian Hooker, *Bureau of Ocean Energy Management*

Steve Lohrenz, *University of Massachusetts Dartmouth*

Ruth Perry, *Shell Exploration and Production Company*

The concluding panel delved into key issues, action items, and needs that emerged from the previous panels as critical starting points for the sectors impacted by offshore wind development and the offshore wind industry.

Collaboration: Panelists strongly emphasized that stakeholders must commit to working collaboratively so that the offshore wind development enterprise harmonizes renewable energy development, fisheries management and livelihoods, and wildlife protections. While significant work has started, many issues remain to be resolved and are critical to achieving co-existence. Open and honest communication that includes engagement amongst

key affected interests is the best path forward towards effective collaboration and getting it right. Panelists highlighted that this goal is achievable if constituent communities collaborate to identify and implement science-based solutions and share the responsibility in funding and innovating the necessary work required. The efforts to be undertaken must be cross-sector, publicly and privately funded, transparent, and collaborative in order to effectively inform management and permitting processes for offshore wind development.

Adaptability: Meeting the challenge of co-existence must be grounded in the best available science, with the understanding that all the information may not yet be available. “Learn and calibrate” must be part of the offshore wind development process; pathways enabling the collection of scientific data should be structured to allow for adaptive management. Construction is a phased process, so if something is not right the first time, there are opportunities to recalibrate as the build-out proceeds.

Establishment of a Scientific Funding Mechanism: Scientific uncertainty is currently challenging the development process and putting our nation’s current scientific enterprise investments at risk. Investment in science and data is congressionally supported and provides adequate funding and resources to the agencies to meet their mandates and thus supports responsible development and co-existence of blue economy resources. Such a mechanism requires the ability to cross funds between agencies and private sectors. For instance, addressing such concerns as interactions between wind and fisheries and protected species requires dedicated resources at the scale necessary, and these resources do not currently exist. This must be a cross-sector effort to encourage federal funding for effective science, management, and permitting processes. Setting aside monies through the leasing and royalty process would create a budget-neutral mechanism to fund the science necessary to support sustainable development of offshore wind.

Regional Approach that Supports and Enhances Our Existing Scientific Enterprise: A regional approach is critically important and can help ensure a balance of environmental sustainability with energy production and coexistence. Our existing scientific enterprise, including our ocean observation systems and federal fisheries and protected species surveys, provides critical understanding towards the effective management of marine resources for all ocean uses. These assets provide the most comprehensive data on marine ecosystems in the world, but they are at risk if we do not adapt them to this new ocean use.

Innovation: We have an incredible opportunity to integrate and leverage tools to advance scientific understanding, to provide real-time monitoring of the marine environment, and support on-going conservation efforts for critical marine species. We can use this massive experiment of offshore wind development to learn more about the ocean through real-time, sustained ocean monitoring and observations. As wind development progresses, we will need to rely on our current scientific enterprise and adapt our scientific surveys and observation technologies so they can be effectively deployed in and around the wind energy areas.

Workforce Development: There is a significant opportunity for greatly increased workforce development for offshore wind projects, the supply chain pipeline, and ancillary areas. The offshore wind industry has already created a significant number of jobs in the science and regulatory space, as well as front-end engineering. The future workforce for this sector will expand upon these areas as well as the operation and maintenance of wind farms as they come online. It was agreed that universities, community colleges, technical training programs, and industry will collectively contribute to the workforce development. Developers can also help make introductions to the supply chain companies with whom they are already working. The U.S. Department of Labor is similarly thinking about who will be getting jobs in this new industry. We need to be smarter before the start by synthesizing these discussions into a strong set of recommendations for Congress.

Identified Needs

PLANNING

- Define the spacing and layout arrangements of wind turbines that may be necessary in order to minimize the impacts to commercial fishing per type of fishing species and gear type.

SCIENCE

- Further define the impacts of noise generation on marine species.
- Further define the noise mitigation capabilities of present and emerging noise mitigation technologies.
- Initiate investigations into possible disruptions to various fish species reproduction. This could include hydrodynamic effects, noise, or physical habitat disruption.

COLLABORATION

- Enhance collaboration between commercial fishing interests, recreational fishing interests, citizen groups, developers, and government agencies for the planning and development of offshore wind farms.
- Continue building a coalition of interests represented at the meeting to work across the sectors and political leadership to establish the necessary funding mechanisms to address science needs.

INNOVATION

- Further define the general science and observations that can be realized from installed offshore wind infrastructure.
- Further develop and test blue technology for construction, especially for the reduction of sound generation and impacts.
- Identify ocean testbeds for technological innovation, focusing on areas of overlapping interests and value, and explore the potential adaptation of land-based technology to oceanic conditions.

We have been fortunate to have the volunteer efforts of an advisory committee during the development of this forum. The committee's collective expertise has been brought to bear on nearly all elements of this event, and we are certain that it would not be this robust and diverse in perspectives, or well-attended had it not had the benefit of their exceptional thought and guidance. We all owe the committee a debt of gratitude. Please join us in thanking the following members for their foundational contributions to this event.

Dr. Jon Hare
NOAA Northeast Fisheries
Science Center

Ms. Annie Hawkins
Responsible Offshore
Development Alliance

Dr. Brian Hooker
Bureau of Ocean Energy
Management

Mr. Hank Lobe
Severn Marine Technologies,
LLC / Sonardyne International
and COL Board Member

Dr. Steven E. Lohrenz
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The Consortium for Ocean Leadership is a Washington, D.C.-based nonprofit organization that represents the leading ocean science and technology institutions — public and private, academia, aquaria, and industry. Our mission is to shape the future of ocean science and technology. In addition to our advocacy role as the voice of the ocean research and technology community, COL manages a variety of community-wide research and education programs in areas of ocean observing, ocean exploration, and ocean partnerships.

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